

EFFECTIVE APPROACH DEVELOPING VOCABULARY USING SONGS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Hojikulov Shukrullo

Senior teacher

UzSWLU

English in primary Education Department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960904>

Abstract: This article is about importance of using songs in teaching English to young learners. Besides, here is given some methods on how to use songs during the lesson. This article consists of methods teaching with the use of songs as the target in the study because listening to music in English is highly motivating for learners and songs are easily accessible for all learners. The prime objective of this article is to investigate whether teaching English vocabulary with the use of songs contributes to developing young learners' better memorization of vocabulary.

Keywords: teaching of vocabulary; songs English language as Foreign language, elements of teaching

Nowadays, the skill of foreign languages, especially English is absolutely required. Therefore, the government wants to increase the quality of teaching English. For those reason, the students must get English lesson early. The government educational institution announces that English should be taught in Elementary school. Elementary school is a compulsory education institutions for young learners to learn English. The young learners will know the basic of the vocabularies, the meaning and the pronunciation of English in Elementary school. Therefore, elementary school should maximize their roles not only in providing and giving the basic materials but also choosing the correct ways and techniques to teach English for students. If elementary school does it well, the students will not get significant difficulties in learning English in the future.

Teaching English to Young Learners has a prime position to be notice. Because given the role and the function of the English language is an international language. As stated by Harmer (1982: 265), that learning English for elementary school based on idea that learning a foreign language or second language would be better if started in the golden age. So, the teaching English for Young Learners is very important because can increase ability about language and to prepare students' basic knowledge before moving into higher level of education. But before the teacher teaches English language for Young Learners the teacher must know about the components or elements of teaching English to Young Learners. As stated by Cameron (2001: vii) the component of teaching English there are learning the spoken language, learning words, learning grammar, learning literacy skills, learning through stories and so on

Speaking is one of the four basic skills: listening, writing, reading and speaking. Speaking skill is the ability to produce sound's articulation and to produce words, to express, to state, to deliver thought, ideas and feeling (Ulviana 2011: 8). Speaking is one of languages that important in language learner as a new second or foreign language. Speaking is very important because by mastering speaking skills, the students can carry out conversations

with others, give the ideas and exchange the information with others. As stated by Nashruddin (2013: 53), that speaking skills is the first that learners want to master.

English language teaching has for quite a long time followed the traditional path-teaching vocabulary and grammar textbooks, cramming students with a considerable amount of exercises and then evaluating their accomplishments through consecutive exams. It is no surprise that English as a Foreign Language learners view English language learning as insipid and an unconquerable obstacle. In fact, English language teaching can be implemented in a relaxed and enjoyable way by using English songs in English as a Foreign Language classes. Songs have been an amusing companion for human beings for as long as or even longer than we can speak. As an integral part of our language experience, it can be of great value to foreign language teaching. And the many-faceted merits songs possess may enrich and activate our foreign language class. Georgi Lozanov incorporates music into his teaching method—Suggestopedia, for music is instrumental in creating a relaxing and comfortable environment, which can propel language learning (Larsen-Freeman, 1985). Besides music, another indispensable element of songs is lyrics which serve as a direct genuine source of teaching materials in foreign language classes, so why should songs be overlooked by the teachers? There have been abundant researches abroad on songs as an authentic teaching resource in language teaching (Maley, 1997; Eken, 1996; Gaston, 1968; Geoff, 2003. This paper endeavors to demonstrate the value of English songs in English language teaching and meanwhile reports several specific teaching activities as serious attempts to work it out in English as a Foreign Language classrooms.

Teaching English vocabulary to young learners sometimes is more challenging than older learners. One of the most reasons is because of young learners' characteristics. Young learners tend to have limited attention span. Moreover they cannot learn better, unless the learning is interesting, meaningful and fun for them (Pinter, 2006).

The use of music and songs in the classroom is something that teachers have been doing for a long time. Using a rhythm to help students remember something, playing a song to help the student relax after a long day of work or rehearsing and performing a song for a special occasion were common things are done in the classroom. Right now, a lot of different reasons as to why use songs in the ESL classes can be found.

Shelley Vernon¹ explains in her article "Using ESL songs" why using songs as a part of ESL teaching has a lot of benefits and gives ten different reasons:

1. Songs help pupils learn vocabulary, grammar and syntax: They hear complete sentences in the songs and absorb grammar and syntax subconsciously helping them to remember words and phrases.
2. Pupils hear meaningful language in context: They hear different words and structures in a natural and meaningful context.
3. Songs are catchy and re-usable: If the songs used in the classroom are fun and catchy pupils will be happy to hear them many times over a short period of time.
4. Songs enhance listening skills: As long as the language used in the songs is within the grasp of the learner, pupils will improve their listening skill by trying to understand what the song is saying.
5. Pupils improve their speaking fluency: They hear the natural rhythm and stresses of English while listening to the songs which improve their pronunciation.
6. Including music and actions in the lessons makes them more appealing: Actions

can be used with any song and not just with the "action songs". This makes the students enjoy the activity and it helps us reach to more pupils since we are using different learning styles.

7. Songs are fun and motivating: Using music lifts the atmosphere in class and brings in a boost of energy making the pupils be motivated and paying more attention.

8. Sometimes songs act as confidence builders: Songs allow students to practice English in a group and achieve more with each listening.

9. Songs are memory aids: Songs stick in our heads and are very useful for English learners.

10. Songs help with classroom management: Songs attract the attention of the pupils and they join in singing or with the actions, in that moment the teacher knows that they are paying attention.

Wright (1987: 10) says that "teaching is essentially social activities, implying relationship between teacher and learners, learners and learners". It implies that teaching is involving active communication and interaction not only between teacher and students but also between the students and their surroundings.

Brown (2000:7) also says that teaching can be defined as "showing or helping someone to learn how to do something, giving instruction, guiding in the study of something, providing with knowledge causing how to know or understand." In short, in teaching activities, the teacher is not only helping students in doing tasks but also guiding them in finding the mistakes and correcting them.

According to Halliwell (1992:23), Recently, language teaching has tended to follow patterns of work which do not help to calm the learners but instead stir them up". It means that language teaching can not make the learners understand and be quiet. It also makes the learners confused. Therefore, "the language teaching should be concerned with real life". (Halliwell, 1992:7) It implies that the language teaching should be taken from the daily life in order to make the teacher can teach the materials easily and the learners can understand it well.

This study was concerned with the stages and activities based on song that were implemented in young learner's English classroom. Moreover the study was also focus on the students' response towards the use of song in their English classroom. In using songs in English Language Teaching, Wherever possible, the selected songs should be fully integrated into the core part of the course, that is the target lessons taught. The songs are used for learning and practicing the main language targets. In short, the use of a song in the language class needs a purpose if it is aimed at yielding a more beneficial result. It is suggested that teachers should continue using music and songs when teaching English because they are effective techniques that can enhance language skills and at the same time create fun in class.

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